

“Exposure Assessment in Mercury”

ImproRisk Scientific Report

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1 Summary

Mercury is a metal that is released into the environment from both natural and anthropogenic sources. Once released, mercury undergoes a series of complex transformations and cycles between atmosphere, ocean and land. The three chemical forms of mercury are (i) elemental or metallic mercury, (ii) inorganic mercury and (iii) organic mercury. Methylmercury is by far the most common form of organic mercury in the food chain. This study focuses only on the risks related to dietary total mercury exposure. In the current report the dietary exposure of the target population is studied using ImproRisk model v.0.3.2. The aim of this risk assessment study was to estimate the dietary mercury intake of the population in Cyprus, to compare this exposure estimate with the Tolerable Weekly Intake (TWI) of 4 µg/kg body weight (b.w.) per week and to calculate the contribution rate of the major food groups to the dietary mercury exposure.

Mean dietary Mercury exposure of the Cypriot population was calculated as 0.514 and 1.48 µg/kg b.w. per week for mean and high consumers, respectively. It was found that less than 1 % of the whole population was exposed over the TWI value of 4 µg/Kg b.w. per week. Much higher exposure was observed for infants, toddlers and other children due to their lower body weight and may be due to their consumption habits, especially in the cases with high fish consumption.

There was no significant difference in Mercury intake between genders and different geographical areas.

Fish (13.1%), pig meat (13.0%), cow milk (11.1%), canned fish (9.7%), and poultry meat (7.7%) were the food categories with the highest contribution to the Mercury intake.

2 Introduction

Mercury (Hg) is a metal that is released into the environment from both natural and anthropogenic sources. It is a metal that occurs naturally in the earth's crust and in the environment. After release into the environment, it undergoes complex transformations and cycles between atmosphere, land and aquatic systems. During this biogeochemical cycle, humans, plants, and animals are exposed to mercury, potentially resulting in a variety of health impacts.

The three chemical forms of mercury known to be present in the environment are (i) elemental mercury, which has high vapour pressure and relatively low solubility in water; (ii) inorganic mercury, which can be far more soluble and which are used in several industrial processes and can be found in batteries, fungicides, antiseptics or disinfectants, and (iii) organic mercury, with methylmercury to be far the most common form in the food chain.

The mercury available on the world market is supplied from a number of different sources, of which the main sources are primary production (mercury mining); secondary production (where mercury is a by-product, for example in zinc production); recycling (from fluorescent lamps, etc.); and reuse of surpluses (for example from the chloralkali industry). Batteries, gold mining and the chloralkali industry are the most important global uses, accounting for over 75 % of worldwide mercury consumption

The largest source of mercury exposure for most people in developed countries is inhalation of mercury vapour due to the continuous release of elemental mercury from dental amalgam. Exposure to methylmercury mostly occurs via the diet. Methylmercury collects and concentrates especially in the aquatic food chain, making populations with a high intake of fish and seafood particularly vulnerable.

2.1 Background

2.2 Terms of Reference

The aim of this risk assessment study was to estimate the dietary mercury intake of the population in Cyprus, to compare this exposure estimate with the Tolerable Weekly Intake (TWI) of 4 µg/kg body weight (b.w.) per week and to calculate the contribution rate of the major food groups to the dietary mercury exposure.

3 Data and Methodology

3.1 Occurrence data

Mercury occurrence data in food were extracted from LIMS for the years 2008-2022. For results below LOD, EFSA's assumption was applied. Occurrence results below the LOD were set to zero for the Low-bound scenario, half the LOD for the Middle-bound scenario and LOD

for the Upper-bound scenario. Dilution factors were applied in order to estimate concentrations for different coffee and cocoa beverages, tea beverages and liquid children and infant milk. Concentrations for mercury in human milk were taken from EFSA's opinion. The aggregated concentration values for fish meat were calculated by excluding the data for large fish as tuna, sharks and swordfish. The aggregated occurrence dataset contained 405 food items.

3.2 Consumption data

Food consumption data were obtained from the EUMenu project funded by EFSA and the dietary survey was carried out in the years 2014-2018. The consumption data was the result of a survey of 1661 participants (male and female). The survey covered all five cities of Cyprus, rural and urban regions, and also all days of the week and the four seasons. The population classes and the number of participants in each class were: [a] infants: 3-11 months (269), [b] toddlers: 12-35 months (279), [c] other children: 3-9 years (300), [d] adolescents: 10-17 years (274), [e] adults: 18-64 years (275) and [f] elderly: 65-74 years (264).

3.3 Food classification

Consumption and occurrence data were both codified according to the FoodEx2 classification system developed by EFSA. At the moment of the generation of the present report the MTX catalogue version 13.1 was applied.

3.4 Methodologies

3.4.1 Chronic dietary exposure

Dietary exposure was assessed at individual level by multiplying the average daily consumption of each food with the corresponding mean occurrence estimated for Mercury summing up the respective intakes throughout the diet and finally dividing the results by the individual's body weight.

3.4.2 Dietary exposure assessment model

Dietary exposure assessment was performed using ImproRisk model version 0.3.2

4 Dietary Exposure Assessment

Table 4.1 presents the substance information.

Table 4.1: Substance information

key	
Chemical Substance	Mercury
Substance Category	Contaminant
Reference value	4 µg/Kg b.w. per week
Type of reference value	Tolerable Weekly Intake (TWI)

Table 4.2 presents the exposure statistics.

Table 4.2: Summary exposure statistics of Mercury

Scenario			
key	LB (µg/Kg b.w. per week)	MB (µg/Kg b.w. per week)	UB (µg/Kg b.w. per week)
Min	0.006	0.023	0.037
Max	20.153	20.609	21.07
Mean	0.393	0.514	0.638
SD	0.654	0.695	0.754
P25	0.119	0.201	0.271
Median	0.223	0.332	0.444
P75	0.412	0.576	0.716
P95	1.267	1.48	1.77
pctOver	0.7%	0.8%	0.9%

* pctOver:Percentage of population above the reference value

Mean and 95th percentile exposure for the Middle-bound scenario were calculated as 0.514 and 1.48 µg/kg b.w. per week (Table 4.2). It was found that less than 1 % of the whole population was exposed over the TWI value of 4 µg/Kg b.w. per week, as also shown in Figures 4.1 and 4.2.

4.1 Distribution of exposure

Probability distribution

Figure 4.1 shows the probability distribution of the exposure.

Figure 4.1: Probability distribution of exposure at the MB scenario

Cumulative distribution

Figure 4.2 shows the cumulative distribution of exposure.

Figure 4.2: Cumulative distribution of exposure at the MB scenario

4.2 Mean Exposure at the MB by Gender

Table 4.3: Summary exposure statistics Gender at MB scenario.

Gender	Min	Max	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	pctOver
FEMALE	0.038	20.609	0.444	0.564	0.181	0.300	0.504	1.311	0.4%
MALE	0.023	20.043	0.587	0.803	0.220	0.363	0.632	1.689	1.3%

Table 4.3 and Figure 4.3 shows that there is no significant difference between the two genders meaning same food consumption habits for male and female subjects.

Figure 4.3: Mean Exposure by Gender at MB scenario.

4.3 Mean Exposure at the MB by Area

Table 4.4: Summary exposure statistics by Area at MB scenario.

Area	Min	Max	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	pctOver
Ammochostos	0.037	6.907	0.463	0.556	0.150	0.255	0.554	1.860	0.3%
Larnaka	0.038	7.226	0.556	0.994	0.185	0.286	0.537	1.734	2.7%
Lefkosia	0.023	20.043	0.520	0.585	0.219	0.367	0.642	1.463	0.3%
Lemesos	0.040	20.609	0.503	0.638	0.220	0.344	0.546	1.327	0.5%
Pafos	0.053	3.950	0.478	0.501	0.205	0.346	0.493	1.463	0%

Figure 4.4: Mean Exposure by Area at MB scenario.

4.4 Mean Exposure at the MB by Population Class

Table 4.5: Summary exposure statistics by Population Class at MB scenario.

Population class	Min	Max	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	pctOver
Adolescents	0.045	3.368	0.575	0.515	0.284	0.400	0.656	1.694	0%
Adults	0.023	7.226	0.440	0.597	0.185	0.303	0.484	1.105	0.7%
Elderly	0.037	3.814	0.323	0.428	0.142	0.217	0.329	0.841	0%
Infants	0.187	20.043	0.878	1.441	0.446	0.575	0.969	1.755	1.5%
Other children	0.151	6.353	1.021	0.856	0.501	0.819	1.248	2.392	2.4%
Toddlers	0.105	20.609	1.233	1.678	0.538	0.792	1.264	3.950	4.7%

In Table 4.5 and Figure 4.5 the exposure of each population class is shown. It was found that toddlers, other children and infants had higher exposure (2 or 3 times) than the other population classes. The lower body weight of these population classes is the main reason for the higher exposure. Also 4.7% toddlers, 2.4% of other children and 1.5% of the infants were exceeding the TWI for mercury intake. Investigating the consumption data it was observed

that the exceedance of the TWI in some cases in these population classes was affected by the high consumption of fish.

Figure 4.5: Mean Exposure by Population Class at MB scenario.

4.5 Mean Exposure at the MB scenario by [Area and Population class]

Figure 4.6 illustrates the mean exposure to mercury by population class and geographical area. It was found that there is no significant difference between the geographical areas in all population classes. The exposure seems to be independent of the geographical area. This is because the population in Cyprus has the same food consumption habits and the foodstuffs that are contaminated by mercury are consumed by all population classes.

Mean Mercury exposure (MB scenario)

Across Area and Population class

Figure 4.6: Cross Plot

4.6 Contributions of different food groups to the dietary exposure

The contribution of each main food group to the total mercury exposure is shown in Figure 4.7. Fish (13.1%), pig meat (13.0%), cow milk (11.1%), canned fish (9.7%), and poultry meat (7.7%) were the food categories with the highest contribution to the mercury intake. It is well known that mercury mostly occurs in fish and especially large fish species. This is the main reason that fish is the highest contributor to mercury exposure. Although, pig and poultry meat as well as cow milk present relatively low mercury contamination, they are highly consumed by all population classes, so they present a significant contribution to the mercury dietary intake.

Figure 4.7 shows the contribution of food items at FoodEx Level 4

Figure 4.7: Contribution to the Mercury Total Exposure MB.

Table 4.6: Contribution to the Mercury Total Exposure (MB). Food items at FoodEx2 Level 4 with greater than 1% contribution

Level1	Level2	Level3	Level4	Contribution
Grains and grain-based products	Breakfast cereals	Processed and mixed breakfast cereals	Cereal flakes and similar	1.96%

Level1	Level2	Level3	Level4	Contribution
Meat and meat products	Mammals and birds meat	Mammals meat	Pig fresh meat	12.96%
Meat and meat products	Mammals and birds meat	Birds meat	Poultry fresh meat (muscle meat)	7.67%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Fish (meat)	Fish (meat)	Fish (meat)	1.06%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Fish (meat)	Freshwater fish	Miscellaneous freshwater fishes	1.30%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Fish (meat)	Diadromous fish	Salmons, trouts, smelts	2.82%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Fish (meat)	Marine fish	Miscellaneous coastal marine fishes	13.12%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Fish (meat)	Marine fish	Miscellaneous demersal marine fishes	1.92%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Fish (meat)	Marine fish	Tunas, bonitos, billfishes	2.90%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Crustaceans	Shrimps and prawns	Shrimps and prawns	1.43%

Level1	Level2	Level3	Level4	Contribution
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Molluscs	Squids, cuttlefishes, octopuses	Squids	2.37%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Fish and seafood processed	Processed or preserved fish (including processed offal)	Canned/jarred fish	9.67%
Fish, seafood, amphibians, reptiles and invertebrates	Fish and seafood processed	Processed or preserved fish (including processed offal)	Structured/textured fish meat products or fish paste	1.57%
Milk and dairy products	Milk, whey and cream	Milk	Cattle milk	11.11%
Fruit and vegetable juices and nectars (including concentrates)	Fruit / vegetable juices and nectars	Fruit juices (100% from named source)	Juice, orange	1.50%

5 Uncertainties

The evaluation of the uncertainties in the exposure assessment of Mercury has been performed following the guidance of the Opinion of the Scientific Committee related to Uncertainties in Dietary Exposure Assessment. Table 5.1 presents a summary of uncertainties, highlighting the main sources of uncertainty and providing an estimate whether each source of uncertainty is likely to lead to an over- or under-estimation of the calculated dietary exposure.

Table 5.1: Summary of qualitative evaluation of the impact of uncertainties on the dietary exposure to Mercury.

Sources of uncertainty	Direction ¹
Different time frame between concentration data and consumption data	+/-
Long-term (chronic) exposure assessed from few days of consumption	+
Measurement error in amounts of food consumed	+/-
Measurement error in individual body weights	+/-
Assumptions taken into account for the preparation of occurrence data	+/-
Level up approach matching in the FoodEx2 exposure hierarchy for the calculation of the exposure	+

¹ + = uncertainty with potential to cause over-estimation of exposure; - = uncertainty with potential to cause under-estimation of exposure

A number of uncertainties can be identified regarding the selection of parameters, such as Mercury concentration levels in foodstuffs and consumption data.

The uncertainty related to the representativeness of the occurrence data for certain food commodities with respect to the number of samples is taken into account. Given the fact that the analytical results were generated with an ICP-MS method in an accredited laboratory, this adds only slightly to the uncertainty of the analytical results.

Some potentially important extrapolation uncertainties arise since an individual survey of food consumption is used to estimate dietary exposure over a timescale longer than the survey duration. Remaining uncertainties relate to the measurement error in amounts of consumed foodstuffs and individual body weights.

In ImproRisk occurrence and consumption data matching for the calculation of the exposure is performed based on a level up approach matching in the FoodEx2 exposure hierarchy, which may lead to overestimation of the exposure.

Furthermore, several assumptions taken into account in the preparation of the occurrence data (data from EFSA, dilution factors, aggregation) may lead to some uncertainties.

6 Conclusions

Mean dietary Mercury exposure of the Cypriot population was calculated as 0.514 and 1.48 µg/kg b.w. per week for mean and high consumers, respectively. It was found that less than 1 % of the whole population was exposed over the TWI value of 4 µg/Kg b.w. per week. Much higher exposure was observed for infants, toddlers and other children due to their lower body weight and may be due to their consumption habits, especially in the cases with high fish consumption.

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3. EFSA (European Food Safety Authority), 2006. Guidance of the Scientific Committee on a request from EFSA related to Uncertainties in Dietary Exposure Assessment. The EFSA Journal. 438, 1-54.
4. EFSA. 2018. Internal report on the harmonisation of dilution factors to be used in the assessment of dietary exposure.

8 Abbreviations

Table 8.1: Abbreviations

Key	Description
BMDL	Benchmark dose lower limit (lower bound of benchmark dose interval)
b.w.	Body weight
LB	Lower bound
LOD	Limit of detection
MB	Middle bound
MoE	Margin of exposure
SD	Standard deviation
P25	25th percentile
P75	75th percentile
P95	95th percentile
UB	Upper bound
wcoeff	Weight coefficient

9 Appendices